

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Fertilizer management—*inorganic sources*

Long-term effects of nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium on irrigated lowland rice in Mekong Delta

P. S. Tan, T. N. Anh, and N. V. Luat, Cuu Long Delta Rice Research Institute (CLRRI), Omon, Haugiang, Vietnam

We studied the long-term effects of NPK on irrigated lowland rice IR64. The clay soil had pH 5.2, 0.3% total N, 4.1 mg available P/100 g, and 0.74 meq exchangeable K/100 g. The experiment

was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications.

N as prilled urea (80 kg N/ha) was applied in three equal splits at planting, tillering, and panicle initiation. P as superphosphate (17.6 kg P/ha) and K as muriate of potash (25 kg K/ha) were basally applied.

Averaged over 5 yr, rice yield was highest with NPK, followed by that with NP for both seasons (see table). Single N or P gave more yield than single K. Grain yield was higher with P applied in wet season (WS) than in dry season (DS) because 2-3 mo before WS the soil was

Effects of NPK on grain yield of IR64, CLRRI, Haugiang, Vietnam, 1986-90.

Treatment	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)	
	Dry season	Wet season
Check (no fertilizer)	3.1 d	2.4 de
N	3.8 b	2.8 c
P	3.4 c	3.5 b
K	3.3 cd	2.2 e
NP	4.4 a	4.3 a
NK	3.9 b	2.6 cd
PK	3.3 c	3.4 b
NPK	4.6 a	4.5 a

^aAv of 5 crop seasons. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

dry; 3-4 mo before DS, it was flooded. P also enhanced the effectiveness of N on yield during WS. □

Effect of potassium application levels and time on rice

E. K. Syriac, P. P. Joy, N. P. Nair, D. Girija, and C. A. Joseph, Rice Research Station, Moncompu, Thekkkara 688503, Kerala, India

We evaluated three K levels and five application times in an experiment to

maximize grain yield and minimize disease in transplanted lowland rice.

maximize grain yield and minimize disease in transplanted lowland rice.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with 16 treatments and three replications during monsoon (Jun-Oct) 1989 and 1990 and wet season (WS) (Nov-Mar) 1989-90.

The soil was hydromorphic silty clay with pH 5.0, electrical conductivity 0.1 dS/m, 0.57% organic C, 16.8 kg available P/ha, and 111 kg available K/ha. MO-11 (120 d) was transplanted at 15- × 15-cm spacing. P was basally applied at 20 kg/ha; N in three splits at 90 kg/ha; and K as

basal (B) at planting, at maximum tillering (T), and at panicle initiation (PI).

Treatments had no statistically significant effects on grain yield during WS. Time of K application significantly increased grain and straw yields during monsoon, with K applied at B + T yielding the most grain (2.7 t/ha). There was no statistical difference among K levels with respect to grain yield (see table).

The increase in rice yield (Y) to K treatment fitted a quadratic response: $Y = 2.19 + 0.015 K - 0.00015 K^2$. □

Grain and straw yields of rice as influenced by K level and time of application. Kerala, India, 1989-90.

Treatment	1989 and 1990 kharif ^a	
	Grain (t/ha)	Straw (t/ha)
<i>K level (kg/ha)</i>		
25	2.5	2.9
50	2.6	3.1
75	2.5	3.1
LSD (0.05)	ns	ns
<i>Time</i>		
B	2.4	3.1
B+T	2.1	3.2
B+PI	2.6	3.0
T+PI	2.4	2.9
B+T+PI	2.5	3.1
LSD (0.05)	0.2	ns
<i>Interaction</i>		
K level × time	ns	ns
Control mean	2.2	2.4
Treatment mean	2.5	3.1
Control vs treatment	sig	sig

^aPooled mean.

Fertilizer management—*organic sources*

Effect of vitamins on spore germination and viability of *Azolla microphylla* sporocarps

R. Shanmugasundaram and S. Kannaiyan, Biotechnology Unit, Agricultural Microbiology Department, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641 003, Tamil Nadu, India

Azolla normally reproduces vegetatively. When conditions are adverse, however, sexual reproduction also occurs. The

Azolla sporophyte is heterosporous, producing both megasporocarps and microsporocarps in the same plant.

We studied the effect of vitamins on *A. microphylla* spore germination. Sporulating *A. microphylla* were heaped and covered with a 10% clay soil slurry. Heaps were periodically sprinkled with water and allowed to partially decompose. After 3-4 wk, the heaps were spread uniformly and dried in shade.

Dried *Azolla* sporocarps (dried frond-based spore inoculum) were soaked in water for 12 h, then sieved.